

PRODUCT OF TWO MATRICES SIMILAR TO COMPANION MATRICES OVER SUFFICIENTLY LARGE FIELDS

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RÉSUMÉ. Dans cette note, on va démontrer qu’une matrice carrée de taille n sur un corps commutatif contenant au moins $2n$ éléments peut s’exprimer comme un produit de deux matrices semblables à des matrices compagnons, c’est-à-dire des matrices ayant le même polynôme minimal et caractéristique, si et seulement si le rang de A est supérieur à $n - 2$, en utilisant uniquement des résultats élémentaires. On donnera également quelques éléments valables sur des corps plus petits.

ABSTRACT. In this note, we prove that a square matrix of size n over a field containing at least $2n$ elements can be expressed as the product of two matrices similar to companion matrices, that is to say matrices with the same minimal and characteristic polynomial, if and only if the rank of A is greater than $n - 2$, using only elementary facts. We will also give some partial results valid over smaller fields.

Keywords : companion matrices, minimal polynomial, characteristic polynomial

1. INTRODUCTION

In this note, all fields considered are commutative. Let \mathbb{K} be an arbitrary field. $0_{k,l}$ denotes the zero matrix of $M_{k,l}(\mathbb{K})$ and I_n the identity matrix of size n . Let $A \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$. We denote $\chi_A(X) := \det(XI_n - A)$ the characteristic polynomial of A (with this definition $\chi_A(X)$ is a monic polynomial), π_A the minimal polynomial of A , assumed to be monic, and $\text{Sp}(A)$ the spectrum of A , that is to say the set of the eigenvalues of A over the field \mathbb{K} . The rank of A is written $\text{rg}(A)$. Let $B \in M_{k,l}(\mathbb{K})$, tB is the transpose of B . Let Ω be a finite set, and let $|\Omega|$ denote its cardinality. Let $n \geq 1$ and $P(X) := X^n + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} a_i X^i \in \mathbb{K}[X]$.

The companion matrix of P is the matrix $C(P)$ defined as follows: $C(P) := \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -a_0 \\ 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -a_1 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & -a_{n-2} \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 & -a_{n-1} \end{pmatrix}$.

These matrices play an important role in the study of square matrices since they are the master pieces of the well-known Frobenius normal form. They are also a useful tool to study polynomials since P is the characteristic polynomial of $C(P)$. Hence, they are matrices of particular interest. This naturally leads us to consider products of companion matrices. We know several results in this direction. For instance, we have an explicit combinatorial formula for the coefficients of product of companion matrices (see [6]) and several results concerning the eigenvalues of such products (see [5]). Note that we also have several results about the decomposition of companion matrices (see [2]).

Considering all these elements, a question arises naturally: Can we decompose a square matrix as a product of two companion matrices? In fact, the particular form of these matrices is a little too restrictive to have a sufficiently large class of matrices satisfying the desired property. For instance, we have the following equality:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & a \\ 1 & 0 & b \\ 0 & 1 & c \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & e \\ 1 & 0 & f \\ 0 & 1 & g \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & a & ag \\ 0 & b & e + bg \\ 1 & c & f + cg \end{pmatrix}.$$

However, we can consider a related but less restrictive problem: Can we decompose a square matrix as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices, that is to say matrices whose minimal and characteristic polynomials are identical? Surprisingly, it seems that there is no answer to this natural question. In this note, we will study this interrogation and prove the following result:

Theorem 1.1. *Let n be a positive integer and \mathbb{K} be a commutative field verifying $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 2n$. A matrix $A \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$ can be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices if and only if $\text{rg}(A) \geq n - 2$.*

This theorem is proved in the next section, using only elementary arguments. Besides, we give, in Section 3, some elements concerning the case of smaller fields.

2. PROOF OF THE MAIN RESULT

The aim of this section is to prove Theorem 1.1 and to give some elements concerning the decomposition studied in this result.

2.1. Matrices similar to companion matrices. We give here some properties verified by the matrices similar to companion matrices. We begin with a useful characterization of them.

Proposition 2.1. *Let n be a positive integer and $A \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$. The matrix A is similar to a companion matrix if and only if $\pi_A = \chi_A$.*

Proof. Suppose that there exist $Q \in GL_n(\mathbb{K})$ and $P \in \mathbb{K}[X]$ such that $A = QC(P)Q^{-1}$. We have $\pi_A = \pi_{C(P)}$ and $\chi_A = \chi_{C(P)}$. Besides, since $C(P)$ is a companion matrix, $\pi_{C(P)} = \chi_{C(P)}$ (see for instance [4] Theorem 3.3.14). Hence, $\pi_A = \chi_A$.

Suppose that $\pi_A = \chi_A$. Let u be the endomorphism of \mathbb{K}^n whose matrix in the canonical basis is A . There exists $x \in \mathbb{K}^n$ such that $\pi_{u,x} = \pi_u = \pi_A$, with $\pi_{u,x}$ the monic polynomial which generates the ideal $\{P \in \mathbb{K}[X], P(u)(x) = 0\}$. Hence, the family $(x, u(x), \dots, u^{n-1}(x))$ is linearly independent, since $n - 1 < \deg(\pi_{u,x}) = n$. So, $\mathcal{B} := (x, u(x), \dots, u^{n-1}(x))$ is a basis of \mathbb{K}^n and the matrix of u in \mathcal{B} is a companion matrix. □

Note that $\pi_A = \chi_A$ if and only if $\deg(\pi_A) = n$ (this is an easy consequence of Cayley-Hamilton theorem). We also have the following characterization:

Proposition 2.2 ([1] Lemma 3.1). *Let n be a positive integer and $A \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$. The polynomials π_A and χ_A coincide if and only if, for every $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{K}^n$, there exists $(P, Q) \in M_{n,1}(\mathbb{K})^2$ such that, for all $1 \leq k \leq n$, $x_k = {}^tQA^kP$.*

The matrices similar to companion matrices appear in particular in the following well-known matrix-completion result:

Theorem 2.3 (Farahat-Ledermann, [1] Theorem 3.4). *Let n be a positive integer, $B \in M_{n-1}(\mathbb{K})$ such that $\pi_B = \chi_B$, and $R(X)$ a given monic polynomial of degree n over \mathbb{K} . Then there exists an $n \times n$ matrix having B in the top left-hand corner, whose characteristic polynomial is $R(X)$.*

We conclude this subsection with the easy result below.

Proposition 2.4. *Let n be a positive integer. Let $A \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$ similar to a companion matrix. The rank of A is equal to n or $n - 1$.*

Proof. There exists $P \in \mathbb{K}[X]$ such that A is similar to $C(P)$. We can extract from $C(P)$ a submatrix equal to the identity matrix of size $n - 1$. Hence, $\text{rg}(A) = \text{rg}(C(P)) \geq n - 1$. □

2.2. Proof of the decomposition theorem. The aim of this subsection is to prove Theorem 1.1. We decompose it into several subresults presented as lemmas. We begin by the case $n \leq 2$.

Lemma 2.5. *If $n = 1$ or $n = 2$ then every square matrix $A \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$ can be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices.*

Proof. Suppose that $n = 1$. There exists $a \in \mathbb{K}$ such that $A = (a)$. We have:

$$A = (a) \times (1) = C(X - a) \times C(X - 1).$$

Suppose that $n = 2$. There exists $(a, b, c, d) \in \mathbb{K}^4$ such that $A = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$. First, we suppose $a \neq 0$. We have:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & a \\ 1 & c \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & d - a^{-1}cb \\ 1 & a^{-1}b \end{pmatrix} = C(X^2 - cX - a) \times C(X^2 - a^{-1}bX - d + a^{-1}cb).$$

Now, we suppose $a = 0$. We have: $A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & b \\ 1 & d-1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$. We set $B := \begin{pmatrix} c & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$. An immediate calculation gives $\chi_B(X) = (X - c)(X - 1)$. By Cayley-Hamilton theorem, π_B divides χ_B and $(X - 1)(B)$ and $(X - c)(B)$ are different from $0_{2,2}$. Hence, $\pi_B = \chi_B$ and $A = C(X^2 - (d - 1)X - b) \times B$. By Proposition 2.1, we have the desired result. □

Remark. If $a = b = 0$, we have: $A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & c \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & d \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = C(X^2 - cX) \times C(X^2 - d)$.

We now consider the case of the matrices whose rank is lower than $n - 3$ when n is a positive integer greater than three.

Lemma 2.6. *Let $n \geq 3$ and $A \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$. If $\text{rg}(A) \leq n - 3$ then A cannot be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices.*

Proof. Suppose that there exists $(B, C) \in M_n(\mathbb{K})^2$ such that $A = BC$, $\pi_B = \chi_B$ and $\pi_C = \chi_C$. The matrix B is not invertible, since otherwise we would have, by Proposition 2.4, $n - 1 \leq \text{rg}(C) = \text{rg}(A) \leq n - 3$. Since the polynomial π_B is equal to χ_B , there exist $P \in GL_n(\mathbb{K})$ and $(b_1, \dots, b_n) \in \mathbb{K}^n$ such that

$$PBP^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & b_1 \\ 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & b_2 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & b_{n-1} \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 & b_n \end{pmatrix} \text{ (by Proposition 2.1).}$$

We have $A' := PAP^{-1} = (PBP^{-1})(PCP^{-1})$. Let $A' := (a_{i,j})_{1 \leq i,j \leq n}$ and $PCP^{-1} := (c_{i,j})_{1 \leq i,j \leq n}$.

Since B is not invertible, $b_1 = 0$. We have:

$$\begin{aligned} A' &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & b_2 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & b_{n-1} \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 & b_n \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{1,1} & \dots & c_{1,n} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ c_{n,1} & \dots & c_{n,n} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \dots & 0 \\ c_{1,1} + b_2 c_{n,1} & \dots & c_{1,n} + b_2 c_{n,n} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ c_{n-1,1} + b_n c_{n,1} & \dots & c_{n-1,n} + b_n c_{n,n} \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

For all $1 \leq i \leq n-1$ and for all $1 \leq j \leq n$, we have $c_{i,j} + b_{i+1} c_{n,j} = a_{i+1,j}$ and so $c_{i,j} = a_{i+1,j} - b_{i+1} c_{n,j}$. Besides, $a_{1,j} = 0$ for all j . Hence, setting $L := (c_{n,1} \ \dots \ c_{n,n})$, we obtain:

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} a_{2,1} - b_2 c_{n,1} & \dots & a_{2,n} - b_2 c_{n,n} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ a_{n,1} - b_n c_{n,1} & \dots & a_{n,n} - b_n c_{n,n} \\ c_{n,1} & \dots & c_{n,n} \end{pmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} a_{2,1} & \dots & a_{2,n} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ a_{n,1} & \dots & a_{n,n} \\ a_{1,1} & \dots & a_{1,n} \end{pmatrix}}_D + \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} -b_2 L \\ \vdots \\ -b_n L \\ L \end{pmatrix}}_E.$$

We have $\text{rg}(D) = \text{rg}(A) \leq n-3$ and $\text{rg}(E) = 1$. Hence, $\text{rg}(C) \leq \text{rg}(D) + \text{rg}(E) \leq n-2$. However, by Proposition 2.4, $\text{rg}(C) \geq n-1$. So, we have a contradiction.

Hence, A cannot be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices. \square

To conclude, we consider separately the cases of matrices of rank n , $n-1$ and $n-2$.

Lemma 2.7. *Let $n \geq 1$, \mathbb{K} a commutative field with $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 2n$ and $A \in GL_n(\mathbb{K})$. The matrix A can be written as a product of two (invertible) matrices similar to companion matrices.*

Proof. First, we consider the case of invertible scalar matrices. Let $A \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$ be an invertible scalar matrix. There exists $\lambda \in \mathbb{K}$, $\lambda \neq 0$, such that $A = \lambda I_n$. We choose n pairwise distinct elements μ_1, \dots, μ_n in $\mathbb{K} - \{0\}$ (this choice is possible since $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 2n$). We define the two following matrices:

$$B := \begin{pmatrix} \lambda \mu_1 & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \lambda \mu_n \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad C := \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1^{-1} & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \mu_n^{-1} \end{pmatrix}.$$

We have the following equalities $A = BC$, $\pi_B(X) = \chi_B(X) = \prod_{i=1}^n (X - \lambda \mu_i)$ (since $\lambda \mu_i \neq \lambda \mu_j$ for $i \neq j$) and $\pi_C(X) = \chi_C(X) = \prod_{i=1}^n (X - \mu_i^{-1})$ (since $\mu_i^{-1} \neq \mu_j^{-1}$ for $i \neq j$).

We return to the general case. We proceed by induction on n . If $n = 1$, the result is true. Suppose that there exists an integer $n \geq 1$ such that, for all commutative field \mathbb{K} satisfying $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 2n$, every invertible matrix of size n over \mathbb{K} can be written as a product of two invertible matrices similar to companion matrices. Let \mathbb{K} be a commutative field \mathbb{K} satisfying $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 2(n+1) = 2n+2$. Let $A \in GL_{n+1}(\mathbb{K})$.

If A is a scalar matrix then A can be written as a product of two invertible matrices similar to companion matrices. We now assume that A is non-scalar (this case is possible since $n+1 \geq 2$). Let u be the

endomorphism of \mathbb{K}^{n+1} whose matrix in the canonical basis is A . Since A is non-scalar, there exists $v \in \mathbb{K}^{n+1}$ such that $(v, u(v))$ is linearly independent. Thus, $(v, u(v) - v)$ is linearly independent. We complete this family into a basis $\mathcal{C} := (v, u(v) - v, w_3, \dots, w_{n+1})$ of \mathbb{K}^{n+1} . The matrix of u in \mathcal{C} is similar to A and is equal to:

$$B := \left(\begin{array}{c|c} 1 & x \\ \hline y & C \end{array} \right),$$

with $C := (c_{i,j}) \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$, $x \in M_{1,n}(\mathbb{K})$ and $y := {}^t(1 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0) \in M_{n,1}(\mathbb{K})$.

We set: $x := (x_1 \ \dots \ x_n)$ and $T := \left(\begin{array}{cc|c} 1 & 0 & \\ \hline -1 & 1 & 0_{2,n-1} \\ 0_{n-1,2} & & I_{n-1} \end{array} \right)$. An immediate calculation gives:

$$TB = \left(\begin{array}{cccc} 1 & x_1 & \dots & x_n \\ 0 & c_{1,1} - x_1 & \dots & c_{1,n} - x_n \\ 0 & c_{2,1} & \dots & c_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ 0 & c_{n,1} & \dots & c_{n,n} \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} 1 & x \\ \hline 0_{n,1} & C - yx \end{array} \right).$$

We have $\det(B) = \det(TB) = \det(C - yx)$. This implies $\det(C - yx) \neq 0$. By induction hypothesis, there exists $(D, E) \in GL_n(\mathbb{K})^2$ such that $C - yx = DE$, $\pi_D = \chi_D$ and $\pi_E = \chi_E$.

Besides, there exists $\mu \in \mathbb{K}$ different from 0 such that $\mu \notin \text{Sp}(D)$ and $\mu^{-1} \notin \text{Sp}(E)$. Indeed, the set $\text{Sp}(D) \cup \{\lambda, \lambda^{-1} \in \text{Sp}(E)\}$ contains at most $2n$ elements. However, $|\mathbb{K} - \{0\}| \geq 2n + 1$. Hence, there exists $\mu \in \mathbb{K} - \{0\}$ such that $\mu \notin \text{Sp}(D) \cup \{\lambda, \lambda^{-1} \in \text{Sp}(E)\}$. This element verify the desired property.

We have the following equalities:

$$\underbrace{\left(\begin{array}{c|c} \mu & 0_{1,n} \\ \hline \mu y & D \end{array} \right)}_F \underbrace{\left(\begin{array}{c|c} \mu^{-1} & \mu^{-1}x \\ \hline 0_{n,1} & E \end{array} \right)}_G = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} 1 & x \\ \hline y & yx + DE \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} 1 & x \\ \hline y & C \end{array} \right) = B.$$

We have $\chi_F(X) = (X - \mu)\chi_D(X)$. By Cayley-Hamilton theorem, the polynomial $\pi_F(X)$ divides $\chi_F(X)$. Besides, $\pi_F(X)$ is a multiple of the lowest common multiple of $(X - \mu)$ and $\pi_D(X)$ (since F is block-triangular). Since $\mu \notin \text{Sp}(D)$, this lowest common multiple is $(X - \mu)\pi_D(X) = \chi_F(X)$. Hence, π_F is equal to χ_F . A similar argument gives $\pi_G = \chi_G$. Hence, A can be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices. □

Lemma 2.8. *Let $n \geq 1$, \mathbb{K} a commutative field with $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 2n - 2$ and $A \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$ verifying $\text{rg}(A) = n - 1$. The matrix A can be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices.*

Proof. If $n = 1$ or $n = 2$ then the result follows from Lemma 2.5. We suppose that $n \geq 3$. Let u be the endomorphism of \mathbb{K}^n whose matrix in the canonical basis is A . Since $\text{rg}(A) = n - 1$, 0 is an eigenvalue of u . Hence, there exists $v \in \mathbb{K}^n - \{0\}$ such that $u(v) = 0$. We complete the family (v) into a basis $\mathcal{C} := (v, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ of \mathbb{K}^n . The matrix of u in \mathcal{C} is similar to A and is equal to:

$$B := \left(\begin{array}{c|c} 0 & x \\ \hline 0_{n-1,1} & C \end{array} \right),$$

with $C := (c_{i,j}) \in M_{n-1}(\mathbb{K})$ and $x \in M_{1,n-1}(\mathbb{K})$. Since $\text{rg}(A) = n - 1$, C is invertible. Moreover, $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 2n - 2 = 2(n - 1)$. By Lemma 2.7, there exists $(D, E) \in GL_{n-1}(\mathbb{K})^2$ such that $C = DE$, $\pi_D = \chi_D$

and $\pi_E = \chi_E$. Besides, there exists $\mu \in \mathbb{K} - \{0\}$ such that $\mu \notin \text{Sp}(D)$ (μ exists since $n \geq 3$ and $|\mathbb{K} - \{0\}| \geq 2n - 3 > n - 1 \geq |\text{Sp}(D)|$). We have:

$$\underbrace{\left(\begin{array}{c|c} \mu & 0_{1,n-1} \\ \hline 0_{n-1,1} & D \end{array} \right)}_F \underbrace{\left(\begin{array}{c|c} 0 & \mu^{-1}x \\ \hline 0_{n-1,1} & E \end{array} \right)}_G = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} 0 & x \\ \hline 0_{n-1,1} & DE \end{array} \right) = B.$$

The matrix F is block-diagonal and $\mu \notin \text{Sp}(D)$. Hence, $\pi_F = \chi_F$. The matrix E is invertible. Hence, $0 \notin \text{Sp}(E)$ and $\pi_G = \chi_G$ (the argument is the same as the one used at the end of the proof of the previous lemma). \square

Lemma 2.9. *Let $n \geq 2$, \mathbb{K} a commutative field with $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 2n - 3$ and $A \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$ verifying $\text{rg}(A) = n - 2$. The matrix A can be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices.*

Proof. If $n = 2$ then $A = 0_{2,2}$ and the result follows from Lemma 2.5. We suppose that $n \geq 3$. Let u be the endomorphism of \mathbb{K}^n whose matrix in the canonical basis is A . Since $\text{rg}(A) = n - 2$, there exist $t, v \in \mathbb{K}^n$ such that (t, v) is linearly independant and $u(t) = u(v) = 0$. We complete the family (t, v) into a basis $\mathcal{C} := (t, v, w_3, \dots, w_n)$ of \mathbb{K}^n . The matrix of u in \mathcal{C} is similar to A and is equal to:

$$B := \left(\begin{array}{c|c} 0_{2,2} & L \\ \hline 0_{n-2,2} & C \end{array} \right),$$

with $C := (c_{i,j}) \in M_{n-2}(\mathbb{K})$ and $L = {}^t(L_1 \ L_2) \in M_{2,n-2}(\mathbb{K})$. Since $\text{rg}(A) = n - 2$, C is invertible. Besides, $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 2n - 3 > 2(n - 2)$. By Lemma 2.7, there exists $(D, E) \in GL_{n-2}(\mathbb{K})^2$ such that $C = DE$, $\pi_D = \chi_D$ and $\pi_E = \chi_E$. Besides, there exists $(\lambda, \mu) \in (\mathbb{K} - \{0\})^2$ such that $\lambda \notin \text{Sp}(D)$ and $\mu \notin \text{Sp}(E)$ (since $n \geq 3$ and $|\mathbb{K} - \{0\}| \geq 2n - 4 > n - 2 \geq |\text{Sp}(D)| = |\text{Sp}(E)|$). We have:

$$\underbrace{\left(\begin{array}{c|c|c} \lambda & 0 & 0_{1,n-2} \\ \hline 0 & 0 & L_2 E^{-1} \\ \hline 0_{n-2,1} & 0_{n-2,1} & D \end{array} \right)}_F \underbrace{\left(\begin{array}{c|c|c} 0 & 0 & \lambda^{-1}L_1 \\ \hline 0 & \mu & 0_{1,n-2} \\ \hline 0_{n-2,1} & 0_{n-2,1} & E \end{array} \right)}_G = \left(\begin{array}{c|c|c} 0 & 0 & L_1 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & L_2 \\ \hline 0_{n-2,1} & 0_{n-2,1} & DE \end{array} \right) = B.$$

The matrices F and G are block-triangular, D and E are invertible, $\lambda \notin \text{Sp}(D)$ and $\mu \notin \text{Sp}(E)$. Hence, $\pi_F = \chi_F$ and $\pi_G = \chi_G$ (the argument is the same as the one used at the end of the proof of Lemma 2.7). \square

All the lemmas contained in this section give us Theorem 1.1.

2.3. Lack of commutativity and unicity. We conclude this section by the two following remarks:

- In general, the decomposition $A = BC$ with B, C similar to companion matrices is not unique. For example:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

- If $A = BC$ with B, C similar to companion matrices then B and C don't commute in general. For instance:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}; \quad \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Note that these two remarks don't use the cardinality of the field.

3. IMPROVEMENT OF THE FIELD CARDINALITY BOUNDS IN SPECIAL CASES

The aim of this section is to give some partial decomposition results over finite fields smaller than those used in Theorem 1.1.

First, note that lemmas 2.5 and 2.6 are true for all commutative fields. Besides, we can easily decompose invertible diagonalizable matrices (and so extend the result used in the beginning of the proof of Theorem 1.1).

Proposition 3.1. *Let A be an invertible and diagonalizable matrix over an arbitrary commutative field \mathbb{K} . The matrix A can be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices.*

Proof. There exist a positive integer n and $(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n) \in (\mathbb{K} - \{0\})^n$ such that A is similar to the

$$\text{matrix } B := \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 & & & & \\ & \ddots & & & \\ & & \ddots & & \\ & & & \ddots & \\ & & & & \lambda_n \end{pmatrix}. \text{ We have } B = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}}_D \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 0 & \lambda_2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & \lambda_n \\ \lambda_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}}_E. \text{ The}$$

matrix D is equal to $C(X^n - 1)$ and the matrix E is similar to a companion matrix since we have:

$$HEH^{-1} = {}^tC(X^n - \lambda_1 \dots \lambda_n), \text{ with } H := \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{\lambda_1} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & \frac{\lambda_2 \dots \lambda_{n-1}}{\lambda_1} \\ \frac{\lambda_2 \dots \lambda_n}{\lambda_1} & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

□

One of the main motivation of Theorem 1.1 was to provide a proof using only elementary results. If we allow ourselves to use more substantial theorems, we can slightly improve the lower bound required in Theorem 1.1 in some cases. For instance, we can consider the following theorem.

Theorem 3.2 (Sourour-Tang, [8] Theorem 1). *Let A be an $n \times n$ singular matrix over an arbitrary commutative field \mathbb{K} and let β_j and γ_j ($1 \leq j \leq n$) be elements of \mathbb{K} . If A is not a nonzero 2×2 nilpotent matrix, then A can be factored as a product BC where the eigenvalues of B and C are β_1, \dots, β_n and $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n$ respectively, if and only if the number of zeros m among $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n$ is not less than the dimension of the null space of A . If A is a nonzero 2×2 nilpotent matrix then A can be factored as above if and only if $1 \leq m \leq 3$.*

Corollary 3.3. *Let n be a positive integer and \mathbb{K} a commutative field verifying $|\mathbb{K}| \geq n$. Let A be a square matrix of size n whose rank is equal to $n - 1$ or $n - 2$. The matrix A can be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices.*

Proof. If $n = 1$ or $n = 2$ then the result follows from Lemma 2.5. We suppose now $n \geq 3$. Let $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n$ be n pairwise distinct elements of \mathbb{K} , with $\lambda_1 = 0$. By Sourour-Tang theorem, there exist B, C such that $A = BC$ and such that $\text{Sp}(B) = \text{Sp}(C) = \{0, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n\}$. We have $\chi_B(X) = \chi_C(X) = \prod_{i=1}^n (X - \lambda_i)$ and $\pi_B(X) = \pi_C(X) = \prod_{i=1}^n (X - \lambda_i)$ since $\lambda_i \neq \lambda_j$ for $i \neq j$.

□

The main focus of this note is the study of products of two matrices that are similar to companion matrices. However, in light of the preceding results, one can readily extend the discussion to products of k matrices of this form.

Proposition 3.4. *Let $n \geq 2$ and $2 \leq k \leq n$. Let \mathbb{K} be a commutative field verifying $|\mathbb{K}| \geq n$. Let A be a square matrix of size n . If $\text{rg}(A) = n - k$ then A can be written as a product of k matrices similar to companion matrices.*

Proof. If $n = 2$ then the result follows from Lemma 2.5. We suppose now $n \geq 3$. We proceed by finite induction on k .

Suppose that $k = 2$. The result follows from the previous corollary.

Suppose that there exists $2 \leq k \leq n - 1$ such that every square matrix B of size n whose rank is equal to $n - k$ can be written as a product of k matrices similar to companion matrices. Let A be a square matrix of size n satisfying $\text{rg}(A) = n - k - 1 = n - (k + 1)$.

Let $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n$ be n pairwise distinct elements of \mathbb{K} , with $\lambda_1 = 0$. By Sourour-Tang theorem, there exist B, C such that $A = BC$ and such that $\text{Sp}(B) = \{0, \lambda_{k+1}, \dots, \lambda_n\}$, with 0 an eigenvalue of multiplicity k , and $\text{Sp}(C) = \{0, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n\}$. We have $\text{rg}(B) = n - k$. Hence, by induction hypothesis, B can be written as a product of k matrices similar to companion matrices. Besides, $\pi_C(X) = \chi_C(X) = \prod_{i=1}^n (X - \lambda_i)$, since $\lambda_i \neq \lambda_j$ for $i \neq j$. Hence, by Proposition 2.1, C is similar to a companion matrix. Consequently, A can be written as a product of $k + 1$ matrices similar to companion matrices.

By induction, the result is proved. □

Remark. By Theorem 1.1, a square matrix of size n , over a field \mathbb{K} satisfying $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 2n$, whose rank is equal to n or $n - 1$ is the product of two matrices similar to companion matrices. Besides, by Proposition 2.4, the rank of a companion matrix is equal to n or $n - 1$. Hence, by immediate induction, a square matrix of size n whose rank is equal to n or $n - 1$ can be written, for every $k \geq 2$, as a product of k matrices similar to companion matrices. If $\text{rg}(A) = n - h$, with $2 \leq h \leq n$, then, by the previous proposition and by immediate induction, A can be expressed, for every $l \geq h$, as a product of l matrices similar to companion matrices.

Proposition 3.5 ([7] Lemma 2.1). *Let $A := \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} & \dots & a_{1,n} \\ 0 & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} & \dots & a_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & a_{n-1,n-1} & a_{n-1,n} \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in M_n(\mathbb{K})$ with $a_{i,i} \neq 0$ and $P \in \mathbb{K}[X]$ a monic polynomial of degree n . It exists $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n) \in \mathbb{K}^n$ such that the characteristic polynomial of the matrix $B = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \dots & \dots & \alpha_n \\ a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & \dots & \dots & a_{1,n} \\ 0 & a_{2,2} & \dots & \dots & a_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & a_{n-1,n-1} & a_{n-1,n} \end{pmatrix}$ is equal to P .*

Corollary 3.6. *Let $n \geq 2$ and \mathbb{K} a finite field. Let A be a triangularizable square matrix of size n whose rank is equal to $n - 1$. The matrix A can be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices.*

Proof. The matrix A is triangularizable and $\text{rg}(A) = n-1$. Hence, A is similar to a triangular matrix with

$$\text{the last row equals to zero, that is to say } A \text{ is similar to } B := \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} & \cdots & a_{1,n} \\ 0 & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} & \cdots & a_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & & \ddots & a_{n-1,n-1} & a_{n-1,n} \\ 0 & \cdots & \cdots & & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

with $a_{i,j} \in \mathbb{K}$ and $a_{i,i} \neq 0$. Since \mathbb{K} is finite, there exists an irreducible monic polynomial $P \in \mathbb{K}[X]$ of degree n (see for instance [3] exercise VII.9). By the previous proposition, there exists $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n) \in \mathbb{K}^n$

$$\text{such that the characteristic polynomial of the matrix } D = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \cdots & \cdots & \alpha_n \\ a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & \cdots & \cdots & a_{1,n} \\ 0 & a_{2,2} & \cdots & \cdots & a_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & a_{n-1,n-1} & a_{n-1,n} \end{pmatrix} \text{ is equal}$$

to P . In particular, $\pi_D = \chi_D$, since π_D divides χ_D (by Cayley-Hamilton theorem) and χ_D irreducible. We have: $B = {}^tC(X^n) \times D$. □

Corollary 3.7. *Let $n \geq 3$ and \mathbb{K} a finite field. Let A be a triangularizable square matrix of size n whose rank is equal to $n-2$. The matrix A can be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices.*

Proof. The matrix A is triangularizable and $\text{rg}(A) = n-2$. Hence, A is similar to a triangular matrix

$$\text{whose last two rows are zero, that is to say } A \text{ is similar to } B := \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & \cdots & \cdots & a_{1,n-2} & a_{1,n-1} & a_{1,n} \\ 0 & a_{2,2} & \cdots & a_{2,n-2} & a_{2,n-1} & a_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & & \ddots & & \\ 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

with $a_{i,j} \in \mathbb{K}$ and $a_{i,i} \neq 0$. Since \mathbb{K} is finite, there exists an irreducible monic polynomial $P \in \mathbb{K}[X]$ of degree $n-1$ (see [3] exercise VII.9). By the previous proposition, there exists $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{n-1}) \in \mathbb{K}^{n-1}$ such

$$\text{that the characteristic polynomial of the matrix } D = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \cdots & \cdots & \alpha_{n-1} \\ a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & \cdots & \cdots & a_{1,n-1} \\ 0 & a_{2,2} & \cdots & \cdots & a_{2,n-1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & a_{n-2,n-2} & a_{n-2,n-1} \end{pmatrix} \text{ is equal}$$

to P . In particular, $\pi_D = \chi_D$, since π_D divides χ_D (by Cayley-Hamilton theorem) and χ_D irreducible. We have:

$$B = \underbrace{{}^tC(X^n)}_E \times \left(\begin{array}{c|c} D & x \\ \hline 0_{n-1,1} & 0 \end{array} \right),$$

with $x = {}^t(0 \ a_{1,n} \ \cdots \ a_{n-2,n})$. We have $\chi_E(X) = XP(X)$. By Cayley-Hamilton theorem, the polynomial $\pi_E(X)$ divides $\chi_E(X)$. Besides, $\pi_E(X)$ is a multiple of the lowest common multiple of X and $\pi_D(X) = P(X)$ (since E is block-triangular). Moreover, $0 \notin \text{Sp}(D)$ (otherwise 0 would be a root of P and P would be reducible, since $n-1 \geq 2$). So, this lowest common multiple is $XP(X) = \chi_E(X)$. Hence, π_E is equal to χ_E and A can be written as a product of two matrices similar to companion matrices. □

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